

PERSON-ORIENTED APPROACH IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11471144>

Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of a person-oriented approach in the process of teaching a foreign language. Based on the analysis, the main aspects and values of the approach under consideration are identified, and the main requirements for the effective implementation of a person-oriented approach are highlighted.

Key words: person-oriented approach, personality, learner, teacher.

The purpose of the article: to determine the content of the person-oriented approach and its influence on the development and formation of a comprehensively developed personality who is able to apply acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities in practice.

In the modern world, it is becoming more difficult to imagine a highly educated, free and successful person who does not speak a foreign language. Knowledge of a foreign language becomes necessary for any educated person, especially during a period of intensive development of all areas of the economy and the gradual «blurring» of boundaries between states and continents. Modern society is undergoing changes in economic, social and cultural terms; these transformations could not but affect the education system.

In the field of education in general and foreign language teaching in particular, student-centered learning is a priority.

Today, the formation of a personality that meets modern needs is one of the leading directions in the field of educational development. Consequently, the need for a modern, independent, active person who makes decisions and flexibly adapts to changing living conditions is growing sharply. Consequently, the relevance of this article is due to the conditions associated with changes in the higher education system, as well as with the growing needs of society for highly qualified specialists. The use of a person-oriented approach in foreign language lessons is one of the main problems in modern teaching. Much attention should be paid to the creation of a universal educational environment in which further socialization of the individual occurs and the professionally oriented skills of the student are developed.

Each student is an individual with his own needs and desires. The teacher needs to take into account all aspects of the person-oriented approach when developing and implementing a foreign language course.

According to N.D. Nikandrov, «the absolute value of society becomes the person, the individual, and the goal of education is the development of the individual» [6, 34]. Thus,

education should act as the basis for personal development and guarantee the social adaptation of students. Focus on the student's personality determines the modern concept of foreign language education, which plays a leading role in the process of personality development.

E. I. Passov was the one who first introduced the term «foreign language education»; he classifies a foreign language not as an «academic subject», but as an “educational discipline” that has enormous potential and can make a significant contribution to human development [4, 6]. Foreign language education is considered as a cognitive, value-oriented, communicative and aesthetic activity, which is of great importance in the formation of new psychological processes and personality traits [1, 33].

Currently, the term «person-oriented learning» is widely used. This means that a modern foreign language lesson should be built taking into account the individuality of each child. And a foreign language lesson is no exception. A lesson is a complex set of educational tasks that both the teacher and students solve based on a specific, purely personal individual situation, the working conditions of a group or an individual student. Each lesson should leave only positive feelings for the learner. The student's interest is the most important condition for achieving success in teaching and education, and, consequently, the success of the teacher.

No matter what a person learns throughout his life, he will always be interested in the quality of the knowledge and skills acquired. Was your time and effort well spent studying? Does the acquired knowledge correspond to the tasks that meet the modern requirements of a highly qualified specialist? How to structure a lesson so that we enrich each other? How to awaken the desire of students to realize their abilities, how to interest them? Each lesson should be novel and exciting in order to maintain students' attention and cognitive interest. All this makes it possible to implement modern technologies for teaching a foreign language, one of which we consider person-oriented learning.

A person-oriented approach provides for educational interaction between the student and the teacher, which in turn makes it possible to form the most complete personality of the student not only through the assimilation of program material, but also through everyone's knowledge of himself, the development of self-esteem, and the desire to share knowledge with others. Modern education is aimed at designing content, forms, methods of teaching and upbringing that ensure the effective development of the individuality of each student, his cognitive interests, personal qualities, creating conditions under which the student can and wants to study well. The goal of a modern comprehensive school is to create the most favorable conditions for the development of the student's personality as an individual, to create psychological and pedagogical conditions that allow working with each individual, taking into account individual cognitive abilities, needs and interests. Let us note that in personality-oriented education, the personality of the student occupies an important place.

The content of curricula and programs should take into account the individual needs of students in the process of actively exploring the world around them. Teachers should be given a certain freedom in choosing the sequence of educational actions and in choosing the pace of work in the lesson. However, the practical implementation of the person-oriented model must be accompanied by regular, objective monitoring of learning outcomes and unobtrusive management of the educational process on the part of the teacher. A person-oriented approach to education does not discard everything that has been accumulated in the theory of teaching a foreign language, but develops and complements them.

Person-oriented education includes the following main aspects:

1. During the learning process, a humane, respectful attitude towards the student must be ensured.
2. The entire educational process should be aimed at developing the intellectual and spiritual abilities of the student.
3. The following are identified as the main priorities of the educational process: the development of the comprehensive personality of the student, his unique individuality, creative abilities, thinking, open-mindedness, the formation of the ability for active and independent activity, the implementation of natural, free development of students.
4. In the process of training and education, the teacher must rely on the subjective experience of the individual, which will allow him to provide targeted assistance to the student, individualize and differentiate training.

The modern lesson is becoming flexible, varied in goals and objectives, varied in forms and methods of teaching, rich in the use of the latest teaching technologies. The teacher needs to combine and implement diverse tasks: on the one hand, to communicate, consolidate, and check the effectiveness of knowledge acquisition; on the other hand, to find ways to include each student in the lesson process, taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

The main value of a person-oriented lesson is the appeal to the procedural side of learning, that is, to how the student learns and how he cooperates with the teacher and classmates. A well-constructed person-oriented lesson changes: the type of interaction between teacher and student (from team to cooperation); the teacher's orientation during the lesson not so much on the effective aspect, but on the procedural side of learning; the position of the student from a simple performer to an active creator; the nature of the learning situations that develop during the lesson, depending on the activity of the students.

Despite the fact that different types of lessons are used in pedagogical teaching practice, depending on the goals and objectives set, a person-oriented approach is an integral component that creates conditions for the motivated practical application of foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities and gives students the opportunity to see the results of their work, receive inner satisfaction, joy and pleasure from it.

Teaching can focus on either a teacher-centered or a student-centered approach, or a combination of both approaches. For centuries, the teacher has been the main link and leader of the entire learning process, and preference was given to teacher-centered learning [4, 85]. The current system of teaching a foreign language requires the use of methods of a student-oriented approach. Authoritarianism should be replaced with humanity, where the learner is at the center of the learning process. However, it should be clarified that this transition is only possible if all specialists at all levels of the educational system take part in it [5, 71-74]. Educational professionals and policymakers should review the nature of the current system and curriculum at all levels and make necessary changes to ensure learner-centered learning.

What requirements can be identified as basic for the effective implementation of a person-centered approach?

Teachers must be competent enough to use a student-centered approach. One of the main tasks of the teacher should be to encourage and motivate students to work hard and actively participate in classes. Teachers should begin to use modern teaching methods, within the framework of a student-centered approach [3, 108-110]. Teachers should try to adapt the

teaching materials used to the requirements of a student-centered approach. Must begin to implement student-centered assessment methods. The teacher must use various means (mass media, social networks, information technology to maintain sustainable motivation among students when learning a foreign language [3, 167-171]. The teacher must create new non-traditional criteria for assessing students, taking into account and identifying the characteristics obtained and introduced knowledge, skills, and abilities. Trainees, in turn, must be prepared to change their role in the learning process.

V.V. Serikov considers the development of a student's personality as:

1) Development of its attributive functions. These include the following functions: selectivity, analysis of reality, arbitrariness, creativity, responsibility, independence. They contribute to the development of the value, conceptual and behavioral aspects of the individual;

2) The development of the spiritual sphere involves the formation of ideological, moral, aesthetic and other values in the form of motives, attitudes and abilities. This group includes the development of language abilities and communication needs of the individual;

3) Activity-behavioral development of an individual is the development of this individual's habits, experience, style and manner of presenting one's "I". In other words, the formation of the individual's speech behavior occurs;

4) Development of the communicative space, namely: the sphere of relationships, social circle, one's own micro society, which involves the development and formation of communicative competence;

5) The formation of the individual's individuality, which is expressed in the formation and development of the individual's consciousness [8, p. 29].

The formation and improvement of the listed personal characteristics should lead to the development and improvement of the student's linguistic personality.

From all of the above, it follows that in language education a person-centered approach to learning is a priority. A foreign language can act as a means of thinking, with the help of which an individual creates the world of his consciousness. Nurturing a humane worldview definitely shapes intelligence, education, culture, empathy, tolerance, and awareness of oneself as a citizen of the world. A foreign language is a means of personal development through solving verbal, educational, every day, personal, professional tasks using foreign language means and is a means of communication that ensures intercultural interaction.

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